

ISic1420

Funerary inscription of Krateas

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

slab

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2013.10.03

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Kasmenai

Place of origin (modern)

near Chiaramonte Gulfi

Provenance

Monte Casale

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 43049

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 47 cm

Width 126 cm

Depth 14 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 80 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. Κρατέα εἰμι σᾶμα τοῦ Εὐπύλ

2. ου

Apparatus

Text of Arena 1998

Translation (en)

I am the tombstone of Krateas, son of Eupylos

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644970

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1420. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4353999>

Photo J. Prag, Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del 06/05/2014